

Table 1: Spitting method scores (ml/min) among the study subjects:

Group -I	Group -II	p value
0.18 ± 0.11	0.29 ± 0.08	0.001*

*-significant difference

Table 2: MST scores (mm) among the study subjects:

Time Interval	Group -I	Group -II	p value
1 st min	6.76 ± 3.94	9.73 ± 2.58	0.001*
2 nd min	12.5 ± 7.39	19.19 ± 4.76	0.001*
3 rd min	19.03 ± 10.28	29.59 ± 6.75	0.001*

*-significant difference

Table 3: Correlation between Spitting method and MST:

Subjects	Spitting	MST	r value	P value
Group – I	0.18 ± 0.11	19.03 ± 10.28	r = 0.873	0.001*
Group -II	0.29 ± 0.08	29.59 ± 6.75	r = 0.805	0.001*
Total Sample	0.23 ± 0.11	24.31 ± 10.16	r = 0.886	0.001*

*-significant difference

Table 4: Association of xerostomia and hyposalivation by MST:

Xerostomia	Group -I		Group -II	
	Hyposalivation		Hyposalivation	
	Present	Absent	Present	Absent
Present	33 (33%)	12 (12%)	9 (9%)	5 (5%)
Absent	40 (40%)	15 (15%)	1 (1%)	85 (85%)

Table 5: Prevalence of xerostomia and hyposalivation:

Groups	N	Xerostomia	Hyposalivation
Group -I	100	45 (45%)	73 (73%)
Group – II	100	14 (14%)	10 (10%)